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Research Article

COMPARISON BETWEEN LICHTENSTEIN REPAIR VS DESARDA IN INGUINAL HERNIA IN TERMS OF POST OPERATIVE PAIN

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Abstract:

Introduction: The estimated lifetime risk for inguinal hernia is 27% for men and 3% for women. Reports on the outcome of inguinal hernia surgery show that recurrence rate 5 years after operation can vary from 0.1 to over 20%. Classically done operations today are tension repairs like Bassini, Shouldice or MacVay's repairs and tension free repairs like repairs done with mesh, plug and mesh or PHS (Prolene Hernia System). All tension repairs have high rate of recurrences and post-operative pain. Sutures are under tension even at rest and gets aggravated during contractions and scar shrinkage in healing process. Therefore, tension free repairs using mesh prosthesis are being preferred.

Methodology: Setting: The Study was done at Dhq hospital Sahiwal.

Sample size: 187 case of unilateral hernia was included in the study.

Sample Selection: Consecutive non-probability sampling

Study Design: Comparative analysis

Data Collection

The study to compare the two techniques of hernia repair was carried out at Department of Surgery at DHQ Hospital Sahiwal. The study group included patients with inguinal or inguinoscrotal hernia during the period of September 2018 to September 2019.

Results: On comparison & evaluation of complications observed post operatively all the P Values are >0.05 which is statistically not significant, implying that both Lichtenstein and Desarda have comparable complication rates. There was no significant difference with regard to postoperative fever, cord oedema, groin discomfort, seroma, surgical site infection, chronic pain, neuralgia and foreign body sensations

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INTRODUCTION:

The estimated lifetime risk for inguinal hernia is 27% for men and 3% for women.¹ Reports on the outcome of inguinal hernia surgery show that recurrence rate 5 years after operation can vary from 0.1 to over 20%. Classically done operations today are tension repairs like Bassini, Shouldice or MacVay's repairs and tension free repairs like repairs done with mesh, plug and mesh or PHS (Prolene Hernia System). All tension repairs have high rate of recurrences and post-operative pain. Sutures are under tension even at rest and gets aggravated during contractions and scar shrinkage in healing process. Therefore, tension free repairs using mesh prosthesis are being preferred. But then there are many associated complications of a foreign body. Laparoscopic hernia surgery reduces pain and duration of stay, but associated with its own complications associated with general anesthesia and instrumentations in addition to the mesh placed inside the abdomen

According to EHS guidelines, mesh-based techniques the Lichtenstein technique in particular and endoscopic methods are recommended for treatment of symptomatic primary inguinal hernia in adult men and Shouldice method has been acknowledged to be acceptable as well.² Lichtenstein method of hernia repair is simple and safe. But the mesh prosthesis has its drawbacks. Mesh works as a mechanical barrier. It does not give mobile and physiologically dynamic posterior wall.³ The synthetic prostheses can create new clinical problems, such as foreign body sensation in the groin, discomfort and abdominal wall stiffness, which may affect the everyday functioning of the patient.⁴ Migration of the mesh from the primary site of implantation in the abdominal cavity is one of the most dangerous complications.⁵⁻⁷ Surgical site infections are more frequent after hernia treatment using mesh.^{8,9} Intense chronic inflammatory process typically associated with foreign body reactions around the mesh prosthesis, the treatment of which becomes a new surgical challenge.¹⁰⁻¹² Additionally, procreation and sexual function are partly seriously affected after surgical hernia treatment with mesh.^{6,13} Desarda repair has removed all drawbacks of both types of repairs. There is no tension on suture lines as seen in tension repairs and there is no foreign body used like mesh repairs

METHODOLOGY:

Setting: The Study was done at Dhq hospital Sahiwal.
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The study to compare the two techniques of hernia repair was carried out at Department of Surgery at DHQ Hospital Sahiwal. The study group included patients with inguinal or inguinoscrotal hernia during the period of September 2018 to September 2019.

Study was approved by local ethical committee. Local informed consent was obtained from all the participating patients after explaining the purpose of the study. All patients with inguinal or inguinoscrotal hernia were eligible for the study. The exclusion criteria were

Patients below the age of 18 years, all complicated inguinal hernia. Obstructed, strangulated, and gangrenous hernia, recurrent inguinal hernia, patients found to have thin, weak or divided external oblique aponeurosis intraoperatively.

Patients with a visible inguinal or inguinoscrotal swelling, presence of cough impulse, inability to get above the swelling, dull aching pain in inguinal region were diagnosed as inguinal hernia. All patients were subjected to preoperative evaluation including history taking, clinical examination and basic laboratory investigations. Elderly patients were subjected to further investigations as part of pre-anaesthetic work up and looked for any complications.

Patients were divided into 2 groups by a team of surgeons to undergo one of the two repairs. Lichtenstein mesh based repair (L group) or Desarda tissue based repair (D group). In this study assignment of patient to surgery was not done by randomization, but by systemic allocation. All patients under D technique were under a single surgical unit, while rest all units in the department performed L repair technique. Anaesthesia was used according to the anaesthetist's opinion after detailed pre anaesthetic evaluation. Oblique inguinal incision was used in all procedures. Dissection and assessment of the external oblique aponeurosis (EOA) was done. Operating time was calculated from skin incision to skin closure.

RESULTS:

In total, 187 cases of inguinal hernia operated during the study duration. 95 in Lichtenstein and 92 in Desarda arm. The baseline characteristics like demographic profile, comorbid conditions on comparison were similar in both the groups (Tables 1

and 2). Clinical characters and hernia features were compared with no statistical differences.

Variables	Lichtenstein (n = 95)	Desarda (n = 92)	P Value
operative time (In minutes)	73.89 ± 12.63	72.60 ± 13.89	0.508
Postoperative pain scores (Sheffield's pain scale)			
POD 1	2.72 ± 0.44	2.43 ± 0.61	0.0003
POD 3	1.56 ± 0.61	1.29 ± 0.65	0.0034
POD 5	0.46 ± 0.54	0.27 ± 0.44	0.009
Return to basic activity (Days)	3.30 ± 1.13	2.54 ± 0.85	0.001
Variables	Lichtenstein (n = 95)	Desarda (n = 92)	P Value
Early complications (<30 days)			
Fever	7(7.36%)	6(6.52%)	1
Cord oedema	11(11.57%)	6(6.52%)	0.31
Groin discomfort	5(5.26%)	4(4.34%)	1
Seroma	2(2.10%)	3(3.26%)	0.679
Surgical site infection	1(1.05%)	1(1.08%)	1
Late complications (>30 days)			
Chronic pain	1(1.05%)	0	1
Neuralgia	0	0	1
Foreign body sensations	0	0	1
No complications	70(73.68%)	76(82.60%)	0.159
Recurrence	1(1.05%)	1(1.08%)	1

On comparison & evaluation of complications observed post operatively all the P Values are >0.05 which is statistically not significant, implying that both Lichtenstein and Desarda have comparable complication rates. There was no significant

Surgical repair of the inguinal hernia is the most common general surgery procedure performed today [19]. The successful surgical repair of inguinal hernia depends on a tension free closure of hernia defect to attain the lowest possible recurrence rate [1].

For years together Bassini's repair and its modifications were standard treatment for inguinal hernia till Lichtenstein tension free repair came. After that there was limited scope for tissue based repairs like Bassini's repair, Shouldice repair etc. In a large multicentre controlled trial, recurrence rates of 8.6%, and 11% were reported after Bassini and McVay repairs respectively [20].

Shouldice repair, is sophisticated technique, requiring long learning curve. It has recurrence rates of <1% at Shouldice hospital and up to 15% in general surgical practice [6], [7], [20]. This rate of recurrence in non-specialist centres shows that Shouldice repair is not a universal repair technique for hernia repair.

Use of prosthetic material for inducing fibrosis thereby strengthening the posterior wall of inguinal canal was principle behind Lichtenstein mesh repair technique. It achieves most of the requirements of an ideal hernia surgery, but the complications related to the mesh are described [10], [11]. Many newer prosthetic materials (Biomaterials) have come to light, but their use in treatment of inguinal hernia is still a question.

Thus the search for ideal operative technique for inguinal hernia with low costs, low complication and recurrence rates, operability by consultants, surgeons in training at smaller and district hospitals, ease of learning and enabling early return to day to day activities. The Desarda technique satisfies most of the criteria of an ideal technique.

The mean operative time was 73 ± 13.63 min for Lichtenstein and 72 ± 13.89 min for Desarda repair. ($P = 0.5$). It was statistically not significant. The similar operating time required is attributed to the fact that time required to fix the mesh is similar to the time required to cut and fix the external oblique aponeurosis in Desarda repair. Youssef et al. , Rodriguez et al. reported significance differences in operative time unlike our results.

difference with regard to postoperative fever, cord oedema, groin discomfort, seroma, surgical site infection, chronic pain, neuralgia and foreign body sensations

DISCUSSION:

The present study had 1.05% incidence of chronic pain in Lichtenstein group and 1.08% in Desarda group, it is found to be of no statistical significance ($P = 1$). The incidence of chronic pain in literature is 49% in Lichtenstein and 0.8–4.8% in Desarda group.

CONCLUSION: Desarda repair is better than Lichtenstein repair in terms of operative time and return to normal activity.

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